

CORDEREAN ANALYSIS ON THE ACADEMIC REQUIREMENTS OF THE PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN A STATE UNIVERSITY: BASIS FOR LANGUAGE CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study structurally analyzed the written academic requirements of the Pre-service teachers enrolled at Cagayan State University. The main instruments were the submitted essays, paragraphs, lesson plans, and written exams. The written outputs of the respondents served as the study's instruments. The evident errors committed by the groups enrolled at the university were classified according to the error types. It was found that the university students have committed numerous errors such as the absence of transitional words, punctuation errors, redundancy, incorrect prepositions used, wrong use of words, run-on sentences, misplaced modifiers, word order, errors on subject-verb agreement, noun antecedent error, etc. The results implied that the respondents need a stronger foundation in grammar. They have not mastered the target language's grammar usage, functions, and rules. This study has pedagogical implications for language teaching and learning. Language professors should incorporate correct grammar usage in all English lessons. There should be more writing tasks or activities given to language learners to enhance their writing skills, especially in Next Normal Education, where students attend face-to-face classes. Furthermore, English language proficiency subjects should be improved along with written communication, and the BEED English courses should be enriched, for these subjects will significantly help the groups refine written communication. Further, the students will be trained to improve their writing prowess before their practice teaching. Moreover, this will help English as a Foreign Language teachers reduce students' writing problems where the English language is directly used. Significantly, this will serve as a vehicle for a more unified teacher-student relationship since the participants have established trust in improving their written outputs.

Keywords: *Language Enhancement, Structural Analysis, Pre-Service Teachers and Written Communication*

INTRODUCTION

Academic writing in Higher Education Institutions is vital because it enables students to ask questions, clarify concepts, and express their thoughts and feelings. It also helps them to develop their critical thinking abilities and find connections.

Students in the university are expected to be good writers, proficient English users, and communicative competent since the students have already completed three English courses during their first- and second-year levels, such as English Language Proficiency 1 and 2, and had completed basic English subjects during their senior high school years, such as Grammar 1 and 2, Writing in the Discipline, Study, and Thinking skills, etc. In addition, the written outputs from third-year college students are expected to be structurally correct as part of the academic requirements in higher education institutions because those English subjects mentioned have a lot of writing drills and research activities where the writing prowess of the students is enriched and enhanced.

Sadly, the checked essays, paragraphs, lesson plans, etc., frequently contain grammatical errors, such as the absence of transitional words, mistakes in punctuation, redundancy, incorrect use of prepositions, incorrect word choice, run-on sentences, misplaced modifiers, errors in word order, errors in subject-verb agreement, errors in noun antecedents, sentence fragments, omissions of commas after introductory elements, misplaced modifiers. During the informal interview, the respondents stated that their writing skills were not fully enriched due to the pandemic's limited training and learning time. Hence, in this Next Normal Education, students could hardly produce refined and free from errors in written outputs.

This predominant circumstance prompted the researchers to analyze the pre-service teachers' written outputs structurally during the Next Normal Education. The results will serve as input for enhancing the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Early Childhood Education (BECED) English subjects in higher education institutions.

This study is based on the Time-on-task Theory established by Corder as a model for teaching English language learners (ELLs), particularly in the BEED Department, emphasizing the contribution of linguistic elements to explaining ELLs' varying levels of accomplishment. (Calanoga, 2019). As mentioned earlier, the idea is applied in this study since the researchers additionally focused on the respondents' current or prevailing writing proficiency status, notably in composition.

The best place to start is by describing the kinds of mistakes that language learners make, as this enables language professors at institutions like Cagayan State University to pinpoint the source of the issue. Linguists have long attempted to do this. As Corder (1967) states, errors occur when the learner modifies the surface structure systematically. So, the error, regardless of its shape or nature, causes them to create the target language.

According to Corder (1967), errors can be divided into two groups. These mistakes are both intralingual and interlingual. These two components speak, respectively, of the

detrimental effects of both the native language of the speaker and the target language itself. The interference of the first language (also known as interference, linguistic interference, or crosslinguistic influence) causes interlingual error because the learner tends to apply their first language knowledge to some linguistic features in the target language, frequently resulting in mistakes. While intralingual error is an error that results from a specific abuse of a particular rule of the target language, it is also the exact opposite of interlingual error in that it focuses on the target language, the target language itself.

The results of Corder's (1971) study, which maintained that authors of research publications should systematically convey research information by adhering to specific rhetorical patterns decided by the discourse community, are relevant to the current study. Failure to adhere to the rhetorical pattern and writing quality will likely reduce the likelihood of approval.

While producing a research article is understandably complex, it is even more difficult if one is writing in one's second or third language. Even if a language editor can iron out grammatical mistakes, researchers are on their own regarding the rhetorical presentation of their research ideas.

However, the former paper differs from the present study in terms of the analyzed instrument—the former analyzed research articles, while the present study explored the students' written communications.

Similar to Corder's study (1973), which focused on analyzing grammatical faults when translating English writings into Bahasa Indonesia text, this study is connected to this. The findings of his research revealed that the errors were on:

1. 85,29% of morphological errors in word formation and 14,70% of affixation errors were found.
2. There were syntactic errors in the phrase (3,96%), clause (1.00%), and sentence (95.04%).
3. The factors causing the translation errors are the students' lack of understanding of the context of the source language text, their inability to construct sentences in the target language grammatically, and their lack of grammar knowledge.

He concluded that the respondents needed to correct their grammar when translating morphological and syntactic English texts into Bahasa Indonesia texts.

The study also shares some similarities with Crompton (2011), who claimed that learners make mistakes in understanding and output. He also mentioned how it can be challenging to attribute comprehension failures to a lack of knowledge of a specific grammatical element of a poorly comprehended sentence.

In his investigation, he built on personal and professional experience in a written composition entitled "My Life in Colombia." Based on Clinical Elicitation (CE) research, he conducted an analysis. The respondents made four errors: omissions, additions, disinformation, and disordering.

The above study analyzed errors using the four classifications of mistakes; however, error types, particularly omission, addition, and disordering, were not considered. Thus, this study was conducted to address them. Then, the results of this investigation were used to devise guidelines for enhancing a language curriculum.

Research Questions

The study was conducted to analyze the linguistic errors in the academic output and requirements of students enrolled at Cagayan State University.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What structural errors are committed in the Literacy Development Class?
2. What structural errors are committed in Teaching Literature in an Elementary grade class?
3. What are the implications of structural errors to Language Curriculum Enhancement based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study is a Qualitative one. Specifically, it employed descriptive analysis to evaluate the linguistic errors in students' academic output and requirements. Descriptive analysis was also utilized since the respondents' written communications were explained and analyzed. This study was conducted with the Pre-service teachers, particularly the BEED and BECED third-year students who took Teaching Literature in the Elementary Grades and Literacy Development, who were the study's participants. Purposive sampling was used in choosing the participants considering Total enumeration, which gave 115 respondents. The examination was conducted at Cagayan State University-main campus, Andrews Campus, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan, Philippines- during the first semester of the 2022-2023 school year.

The written outputs of the pre-service teachers, such as essays, paragraphs, and lesson plans, particularly the BEED and BECED third-year students who took Teaching Literature in the Elementary Grades and Literacy Development, were analyzed using error analysis.

Regarding data collection, the students' written outputs were read intensively and classified according to subjects and types of errors. After the checking and analyses, the outputs were returned to the students, and feedback was given virtually and face-to-face. Students also had the chance to rewrite their written outputs by incorporating the researcher's suggestions.

Lastly, the information gathered was divided into categories depending on the types of errors made, and those categories were then examined using the Error Analysis of Dafei (2007), Haggetry, John (2007), and Iyldyz (2007). The study concentrated on structural errors, emphasizing mistakes that are deliberate breaks with the input patterns to which the participants have been exposed.

RESULTS

1. Structural Errors in Literacy Development Class

Table 1. Structural Errors in Literacy Development Class.

Sample sentences/phrases	Errors committed	Errors Analysis
For me the most helpful in developing the literacy of	Incomplete sentences Lack of parallel structure	The transition of the sentences is vague. It

<p>early learners is the Marungko approach. Because the children will start with each sound of the letter first. And then the short words that fit the sounds and the letters.</p> <p>As a teacher you need to be prepared for the things you will encounter.</p> <p>The marungko approach, because it helps students to improve their reading skills through the use of modern Filipino. It's one of a great helper for young learners for them to know the Alphabet.</p> <p>For me, best approach that is best use on teaching young learners in barrio school are the four -pronged approach</p> <p>Because in this approach teacher will help the student develop their genuine love for reading, critical thinking, mastery of oral language structure, and beginning reading.</p> <p>If I am a Pre-school teacher in a barrio, i will seek help for government to have fund that will be use to buy books or other materials that's need in school.</p> <p>For me, I will be use my creativity, for example, I will make a way like if there is no TV in the room</p> <p>It is better to teach children to read tagalog first.</p> <p>Ms. Patrice shall use Distar Approach, because she handle a varied types of learners</p>	<p>missing comma after introductory element</p> <p>missing comma after introductory element</p> <p>A comma is used incorrectly.</p> <p>Absence of article "the" in indicating the superlative degree of adjective</p> <p>missing comma after introductory element misspelled word</p> <p>capitalization Tense of the verb error</p> <p>Error on Subject-verb agreement</p> <p>Wrong choice of word.</p> <p>A comma is used incorrectly. Subject-verb agreement error</p>	<p>lacks a parallel structure.</p> <p>There is an absence of a comma after the word teacher.</p> <p>The sentence is not concise/ not clear (Better to use using instead of through the use)</p> <p>Type of Error: Addition The word best is not necessary to be a part of the sentence.</p> <p>No comma is found after the approach, The word beginning is misspelled.</p> <p>I must be capitalized. The present form "use" is incorrect. The past form of used is needed in the sentence.</p> <p>The verb is in the future progressive tense; thus, a verb with "ing" like "using" is correct to be used. Wrong choice of word It is better to use Filipino instead of Tagalog when referring to language A comma is used, yet it is not necessary. The verb "need" is used instead of the S-form of</p>
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<p>...in whole language approach that teacher are expected to provide a literacy Teacher Fe's first step to do is to invite her students what they already realize Marungko Approach is the best in teaching young learner's in barrio schools because whenever it is barrio they can teach young learner's the modern Filipino alphabet with or without the use of any materials. I think I will seek for help to those who wants to share any amount I think Ms. Patrice will use will be Four-pronged Approach because her young learners has different types of reading. Ms. Patrice needs to deal with the interest of learner's to pay their attention. She should teach them the way that no one will left behind in reading. -For me the four-pronged approach. Because this approach has components where children exhibit for them to learn more. Including their love for reading, developing critical thinking, mastery of oral language structures and etc. They can also engage different activities that will enhance their critical thinking. Which is they can work as a group or independently. It also help them build or develop their decision</p>	<p>Subject-verb agreement error</p> <p>Wrong tense of a verb</p> <p>Plural form of the noun error Wrong spelling</p> <p>Subject-verb agreement error</p> <p>Modal error Auxiliary verb error Subject-verb agreement error Plural form of the noun is needed not a possessive form Absence of be-verb</p> <p>Run on sentence sprawl Vague thought Lack of parallel structure Wrong conjunction used.</p> <p>Fragment Misplaced modifier Subject-verb agreement error</p>	<p>the verb, "handles" since the subject pronoun, "she" is singular in form</p> <p>The plural linking verb, are, is used instead of "is"</p> <p>Past form of the verb is not used.</p> <p>Plural form of the noun is needed not a possessive form. The word alphabet is misspelled.</p> <p>Since those is used, the verb must be want</p> <p>The modal, will, is used repeatedly. The auxiliary verb "has" is incorrect; rather, have is needed since the subject is teachers. The absence of be-verb is needed. Better:....will be left behind</p> <p>The sentences are not written completely. The construction is fragmented</p> <p>The sentences are not written completely. The construction of the sentence is fragmented. Wrong phrasing/ construction of sentences not concise.</p>
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<p>making, connection with other young learners.</p>	<p>The verb help is used. It is must be S-form of the verb since the singular subject pronoun "It" is used.</p>	
<p>For me the Marungko Approach because it's highlight the mother tongue first, before introducing borrowed letters and words. And it is needed especially in barrio schools for those who don't have totally access to the materials that is needed in a one classroom. And this approach is the best which can learn the learners in a barrio school. In addition using this methods the highlight things already familiar to our students will make learning easier for them, and more fun as well. As a future preschool teacher, I will go to the government and ask a help. To ask a fund it is not for us as a teacher but rather for children. For them to have a better learning, better experience, better materials, resources to access. So that they will not struggling for their studies because of lack of materials</p>	<p>Contracted word error SVA error Run-on sentence sprawl Wrong plural form of demonstrative pronoun Redundancy Wrong spelling Missing comma after introductory element SVA error</p>	<p>Vague thought The sentences are not coherently written. It lacks parallel structure. Article "a" is used already; so, no need to use "one" The pronoun this is used instead of these.</p>
<p>Having time management, and self-conditioning. Amidst the challenges they experienced, teacher Fe must aware of the technology surrounding them, that her pupils has a poor or limited materials for reading and etc.</p>	<p>Wrong plural indefinite pronoun used Run on / sentence sprawl Absence of be-verb Wrong punctuation usage</p>	<p>Help is a mass noun; thus, some must be used and not "a" Sentences are not coherently written. It lacks transitional devices.</p>
<p>To make her teaching-</p>	<p>Subject-verb agreement error Run-on sentence sentence sprawl Absence of be-verb Subject-verb agreement error conjunction is incorrectly used. Wrong punctuation usage Subject-verb agreement</p>	<p>-Sentences are not coherently written. -It lacks transitional devices. -The auxiliary <i>have</i> must be used instead of has -Absence of be-verb after the phrase --"Teacher Fe must be aware" -Omit conjunction "and" before etc. The first letter of the word</p>

learning useful and enjoyable, She must already surfed on the web and downloaded educational videos. She must organiz and plan how much a she spends on specific activities which is very important.	error Run-on Lack of parallel structure Wrong spelling Article is incorrectly used. Preposition error SVA error	She is capitalized. Preposition “on” is added, it must be omitted instead. Linking verb “is” is used; it contradicts the number of the subject, activities <i>Type of Error: Disorder</i>
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Table 1 shows the sample sentences and paragraphs of the respondents. Likewise, it shows the structural errors committed by the third-year students who are taking Bachelor of Early Childhood Education and finished Literacy Development subject. The respondents answered four questions related to approaches to teaching Literacy Development. The students were given three (3) days to complete their written tasks to finalize and proofread their written outputs. Expectedly, their answers must be free from grammatical lapses since they had sufficient time to do so. However, it was found that their written outputs have errors.

As seen in Table 1, the sentences are not entirely written; their construction is fragmented. Students also needed to correct phrasing or structure sentences concisely.

Similarly, some of the paragraphs in the table have vague thoughts, and the organization of sentences is not well-organized. In addition, the sentences are not coherently written, lack parallel structure, lack transitional devices, and have tense of verb errors.

2. Structural Errors in Teaching Literature in Elementary Grade Class

Table 2. Structural Errors in Teaching Literature in the Elementary Grades Classes.

Sample sentences/phrases	Errors committed	Error analysis
I. Objectives: At the end of the lesson, the pupils should be able to:	Wrong modal used	The modal <i>will</i> is appropriate instead of should
I. Preliminaries “Have you pray?”	Subject-verb agreement error	The verb used is not in the past participle form, yet the sentence talked of the perfect tense.
“before you seat please pick up the pieces of paper under your chair”	Capitalization error Wrong choice of word	Sit must be used instead of a seat
“before we proceed to our lessons for today the day, I will check your attendance first”	not concise (use of the day)	Using the phrase “the day” made the sentence wrong Classification of Error: Addition
Before we move on (remove) to our next lesson, what did we discussed yesterday?”	Tense of verb error Pronoun used is not fitted	The pronoun “on” may not necessarily needed in the sentence. Classification of Error:

Sample sentences/phrases	Errors committed	Error analysis
II. Presentation Please stand up and we will going to watch a video and try to sing and follow it.	Redundancy Absence of be-verb	Addition The word up must be removed. The verb be is omitted.
Who are your favorite cartoon character?	Subject-verb agreement	The plural form of the verb (are) is used, yet the noun (character) is singular The first letter of "who" should be in small letter.
After that, Who can give me the activities they do all over the moon?	Capitalization error Tense of verb error	The verb "did" is needed to indicate past action. The action word "noticed" is used, the sentence needs present base form, notice.
What did you noticed on the pictures	Punctuation error Subject-verb agreement error	Rule: When using do, does, and did, the verb must be in the present base form. Verbs/words are in the plural form; hence, the verb "show" is appropriate
Verbs are words that shows action.	Subject-verb agreement error	
When the two boy finally arrived to the moon, what did they do first?	Plural form of noun error	Plural form of noun is needed
Are they any questions about verbs?	Wrong pronoun	A subject pronoun is used instead of the demonstrative pronoun "there"
Verbs are use to describe an action word Teacher! Create at least 10 sentences that has a verb or action words that you do everyday.	Tense of verb error Wrong punctuation Subject-verb agreement error	In the sentence, past form "used" is needed. Sentences is the referent, thus, the auxiliary verb "have" must be used
What do we call these all words class?	excessive word usage	The word all is added in the sentence. It is better if this is omitted The action word "learned" is used; the sentence needs to present base form "learn."
What lesson did you learned from the short story?	Subject-verb agreement error	Rule: When using do, does, and did, the verb must be in the present base form.
They are Common and Proper Noun Ma'am	Wrong plural form of nouns Absence of a	The thought of the sentence referred to two things (common and proper nouns);

Sample sentences/phrases	Errors committed	Error analysis
Discussion: I have flash cards here and you need to read it and identify its elements.	punctuation Noun-pronoun antecedent error	thus, nouns must be used. Correct way: The plural form, flashcards, need plural pronouns flashcards – those- their The interrogative pronoun who is fitted and not what since the thought refers to characters.
What are the characters of the story?	Wrong pronoun used	
D. Generalization What are the two kind of nouns we have discussed class? Never think that you can't, instead find more opportunities to become succeed.	Error in stating the plural form of a noun Wong abstract noun Wrong choice of word	Kinds of a noun is better way Succeed is not fitted in the sentence; it is better if it is successful.
Can anyone tell me what does the card says?	Subject-verb agreement error	Does is used in the sentence; hence, say is needed The sentence is vague. Better if: Does anyone know the setting of the story?
Does anyone know what a setting of a story is? Very good! But where did the story took place?	Sentence sprawl Tense of a verb error	The verb take is appropriate because did is used. Rule: The verb must be in the present base form when using do, does, and did.
Activity 1: Look at the pictures class, the heart is posted on the board that you must color it. Red if the words are Common nouns; Blue if it's Proper nouns.	Vague instructions Not concise	Lack of parallel structure Better if: Color those hearts red if the words are common nouns and blue if those are proper nouns.
IV. Evaluation Direction: In underlined words, identify the statement and write PN if it's a proper noun and CN if it's a common noun in each sentence	Wrong word usage Instructions are not clear.	Directions must be used instead of Direction because it refers to instructions. Better: Write PN if the underlined noun is a proper noun and CN if it is a common noun.
Assignment: Find a story you like, list the story's elements	Run-on sentence Vague instructions Absence of	Instructions are not vivid. Transitional words should be coherently used.

Sample sentences/phrases	Errors committed	Error analysis
(characters, setting, theme, and plot), and then in a four sentence paragraph describe what you like and why you like it.	Transitional words Plural form of a noun error	<i>Type of Error: Disorderliness</i>

As Table 2 shows, the sentences and statements of the students in their lesson plans in teaching literature class showed various structural errors. The table shows the crafted objectives were erroneous because the models used were inappropriate. Similarly, in the preliminaries and presentation part of the lesson plan, the pre-service students committed tense of verb and subject-verb agreement errors. Moreover, the lesson plan's discussion, application, evaluation, and assignment errors were in run sentences, sentence sprawl, vague instructions, and subject-verb agreement.

In connection, the third-year Bachelor of Elementary Education students who finished Teaching Literature in the Elementary Grades were tasked with making lesson plans in English for any grade level. The submitted outputs were checked and resent to the pre-service teachers so they could incorporate the corrections and suggestions. The respondents were given chances to rewrite and re-edit their outputs after revisions.

3. Implication of Structural Errors to Language Curriculum Enhancement Based on the Results of the Study

Finally, this study sought to answer the third question: What are the implications of structural Errors for language curriculum enhancement?

After analyzing Structural Errors in Literacy Development Classes and Teaching Literature in Elementary Grades Classes, the study inferred that structure errors affect each sentence's message. The results show that errors also affect the coherence of messages presented in a paragraph. In many other instances, effective language structures play a pivotal role in promoting the readability and clarity of messages. The results implied that the respondents have a weak foundation in grammar. They have not mastered the target language's grammar usage, functions, and rules. This study has pedagogical implications for language teaching and learning. Language professors should try to incorporate correct grammar usage in all English lessons and curricula. There should be more writing tasks or activities given to language learners to enhance their writing skills, especially in Next Normal Education, where students attend face-to-face classes. Furthermore, English language proficiency subjects should be improved along with written communication, and the BEED English courses should be enriched, for these subjects will significantly help the groups refine written communication. The students will be trained to improve their writing prowess before their practice teaching. This study will help English as a Foreign Language teachers reduce students' writing problems where the English language is directly used. Significantly, this will serve as a vehicle for a more unified teacher-student relationship since the participants have established trust in improving their written outputs.

DISCUSSION

Structural Errors in Literacy Development Class

There are numerous errors committed by third-year college students in their constructed sentences and paragraphs, such as subject-verb agreement errors, modal errors, auxiliary verb errors, the plural form of the noun is needed, not a possessive form absence of be-verb, run on, sentence sprawl, vague thought, lack of parallel structure, wrong conjunction used, fragment, misplaced modifier, contracted word error, the incorrect plural form of the demonstrative pronoun, redundancy, wrong spelling, missing comma after introductory element and wrong choice of word.

In summary, the respondents' apparent and frequent mistakes included a lack of parallel organization, sentence sprawl, fragment, subject-verb agreement problems, run-on phrases, incorrect verb tense, and incorrect word usage. This finding implies that even if the respondents are already in third-year college, they still have not mastered grammar rules. Their writing skills are not yet fully enhanced. This further implies that the students have a weak foundation in terms of grammar usage. Their outputs are not syntactically and structurally bound with the standard for writing essays, paragraphs, and other related written outputs.

During the informal interview with the respondents, which was conducted after analyzing their written outputs, they narrated that they were not fully linguistically and communicatively competent. This can be attributed to the kind of grammar foundation and orientation they had during the Pandemic period. Their poor command of English is attributed to their first language interference in learning the target language. This reality is related to the findings of MacSwan (2017) that the first language interferes with understanding and learning the English language.

Further, this coincides with Malana (2018), Maleki et al. (2007), and Silalahi (2018) as they claim that predominant errors have been repeatedly committed in grammar and mechanics by university students, which alarmed the language teachers.

Structural Errors in Teaching Literature in Elementary Grade Class

There are structural errors committed by the third-year students in their Teaching Literature in the Elementary Grades. The lesson plans analyzed showed that numerous errors were engaged in the different parts of the lesson plans.

The common errors were a lack of parallel structure, subject-verb agreement, run-on sentences, vague instructions, sentence sprawl, verb tense, and wrong word usage.

This result suggests that the student's foundational knowledge of grammatical usage is weak. Their outputs are not syntactically and structurally bound with the standards in composing lesson plans and other associated written outputs.

Further, this implies that the respondents still need more writing training and drills. Although they are already third-year college students, they must still review and perfect the grammatical standards. Their writing skills will be improved before they are deployed to different Elementary schools next year.

The findings were counter-validated through an informal interview with the respondents and a post-conference after their classroom teaching demonstrations. The

respondents revealed that writing lesson plans in straight English is a significant challenge. Producing a refined lesson plan needs time, effort, and training. They also indicated they are not fully linguistically competent due to their limited language exposure and writing training for the past two years. During the Pandemic period, their written skills were fully enhanced or enriched.

These findings conform to Suryani et al.'s (2014) and Tamayo & Catabay (2018) studies. Similarly, the concept of Vasquez (2008) is related to the results that proficiency is a more complex topic than is generally assumed. The validity of proficiency in L2 education is helpful for careful consideration when building the English as an International Language (EIL) competence framework.

Conclusions

Based on this study's findings, it is concluded that pre-service teachers are not proficient writers, even if they studied many English subjects during their senior high school and their first two years of university. Due to their insufficient writing expertise in the English language, they could not produce polished written communications and outputs that adhered to proper structural conventions.

The language learner and professor must be committed to and willing to learn a foreign language. Restructuring and modifying the instructor's point of view and revisiting his or her teaching methodologies and strategies to close and fill the students' gaps in grammar usage, error, and structural analyses are unquestionably vital and relevant instruments in language education. A professor can make better choices that will improve performance and enable them to meet current pedagogical and professional demands when they are aware of the types of errors their students in the university are making and their potential causes.

The textual outputs from this study show us that mistakes or structural analysis serve the goal of teaching the English language. Also, it may alter how much students are aware of their faults. Consequently, they will learn new information and improve their communication skills. By highlighting their mistakes, professors can influence students' cognitive processes and learning changes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, it is recommended that the pre-service teachers in the university must have varied enriching writing activities in English classes to improve their writing prowess.

English instructors should conduct writing remedial classes when necessary. They also need feedback. Instructors must return the checked written outputs to the students so they are aware of their errors in writing paragraphs and essays. This will enrich their writing skills.

In addition, university-wide syllabi should be calibrated to address the needs and concerns of Pre-service teachers regarding writing problems and grammar usage.

The study findings affect language teaching, learning, and language curriculum. The proposed enhanced Purposive Communication, English Language Proficiency, Literacy Development, and Teaching English in Elementary subjects should be

intensified. These courses will greatly aid the student's ability to produce polished written work. Additionally, the Pre-service teachers will be trained to improve their writing competencies. Furthermore, this will help the Pre-service teachers in making refined lesson plans and other related written communication where the English language is straightly used as stipulated in the enhanced Program Intended Learning Outcomes of the Program, which is based on CMO No. 75, s. 2017 that students must possess broad knowledge of language and literature for effective teaching and learning and demonstrate proficiency in oral and written communication for different purposes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the research, ethical approval was obtained from the university's Research Ethics Board. Written consent forms were provided to all participants. After receiving their consent and assuring them of anonymity and confidentiality, they were asked to submit their written output for analysis with the researchers. The researchers then assured the confidentiality of their personal information by not mentioning their names.

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